

COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE AS THE MAIN GOAL OF TEACHING ENGLISH AS A SECOND FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *The relevance of the studying on a multilingual basis as a basic component of in-depth language education is determined, first of all, by the general global trend towards integration in the economic, cultural and political spheres, which in the educational sphere determines the tendency towards the integration of subject knowledge, a focus on understanding the holistic picture of the world [1]. The purpose of the article is to theoretically explain the concept of multilingualism or multilingualism, identify the features of multilingual education, study modern methods in multilingual education, as well as the practical development of one's own methodology for teaching English as a second foreign language.*

Keywords: Oral and written speech, speech activity, social interaction, bilingual, multilingual schools, learner-centered learning.

In the era of globalism, a multilingual person is a guardian of cultural heritage and regional realities, a mediator between different peoples and ethnic groups. Requirements for specialists in the field of contacts with foreign partners in highly specialized areas of economics, industry and science are increasing [2].

Modern researchers talk about the need to develop special methods and models of polylingual education for polylingual students and the development of bilingualism in monolingual Teaching a second foreign language has its own specifics, since, unlike other subjects, the main goal of teaching is the development of students' communicative competence. Currently, the global goal of mastering a second foreign language is considered to be familiarization with another culture and participation in the dialogue of cultures. This goal is achieved by developing the ability for intercultural communication [3]. It is teaching organized on the basis of tasks of a communicative nature, teaching foreign language communication, using all the tasks and techniques necessary for this, that is a distinctive feature of a foreign language lesson [4].

Foreign language communication is based on the theory of speech activity. Communicative teaching of a foreign language is activity-based in nature, since verbal communication is carried out through "speech activity", which, in turn, serves to solve the problems of productive human activity in the conditions of "social interaction" of communicating people [5]. Participants in communication try to solve real and imaginary problems of joint activity with the help of a foreign language.

The humanistic approach involves learner-centered learning. This means that learning, or more precisely, students interacting with each other, is the center of cognitive activity in the lesson. The initial stage of teaching a second foreign

language in secondary school is understood as the period of studying a second foreign language [6], which makes it possible to lay the foundations of communicative competence, necessary and sufficient for their further development and improvement in the course of studying that subject.

It takes quite a long time to lay the foundations of communicative competence, because students need to become familiar with the target language as a means of communication from the very first steps. This means that they must learn to understand foreign language speech by ear (listening) [7], express their thoughts using the language they are learning (speaking), read, that is, understand a foreign language text read silently, and write, that is, learn to use the graphics and spelling of a foreign language when performing written tasks aimed at mastering reading and speaking, or being able to express one's thoughts in writing. Indeed, in order to lay the foundations for each of the listed types of speech activity, it is necessary to accumulate linguistic means that ensure the functioning of each of them at an elementary communicative level, allowing them to move to a qualitatively new stage of their development in the future [8].

The initial stage is also important because success in mastering the subject at subsequent stages depends on how learning proceeds at this stage. One cannot but agree with the English methodologist G. Palmer [9], who attached great importance to the beginning in the study of a foreign language. So, he wrote: "Take care of the first two stages and the rest will take care of itself." Although, this statement mentions the intermediate stage in addition to the elementary stage, this does not remove the importance of the first, that is, the initial stage.

In addition, it is at the initial stage that the methodological system underlying the teaching of the second foreign language is implemented, which from the first steps allows the teacher to enter this system and carry out the educational process in accordance with its main provisions [10].

As is known, the structure of the initial stage can be different in relation to the language material, its volume, organization; sequence in the formation and development of oral and written speech; taking into account the conditions in which the educational process is carried out; revealing the potential of the subject itself in solving the educational, developmental and developmental tasks facing the university [11].

That is why the initial stage in studying a second foreign language allows you to lay the foundations of communicative competence, necessary and sufficient for their further development and improvement in the course of studying the subject, models of multilingual education aimed at preserving the language of a national minority, or models that reteach from the language of emigrants to the language of the majority in accordance with various methodological approaches to organization of training [12].

The modernization of higher education is associated, first of all, with a qualitative update of the content and ensuring its developmental, culturally appropriate nature. In this regard, special attention is paid to creating conditions for the development of the student's creative personal potential and expanding the possibilities of modern in-depth education, including language education. Within the

framework of advanced language education, such conditions arise in the process of learning on a multilingual basis. Meanwhile, in recent years, the problem of bilingual education has been increasingly discussed, and the relevance and progressiveness this technology is confirmed. Education in conditions of bilingualism is recognized by many scientists as one of the possibilities for the most effective development of teaching a foreign language at school and therefore is currently the focus of attention of researchers. At the beginning of the 21st century, bilingual education is seen as a very promising direction. Many scientists advocate the introduction of bilingual teaching of a foreign language and believe that the success of the matter is ensured if the number of multilingual schools and classes is increased.

Polylingual education allows for deep penetration into the culture of another people, expands the possibilities for the active use of a foreign language, which is a prerequisite for the successful adaptation of graduates to the conditions of the pan-European market.

Teaching a second foreign language has its own specifics, since, unlike other subjects, the main goal of teaching is the development of students' communicative competence. Currently, the global goal of mastering a second foreign language is considered to be familiarization with another culture and participation in the dialogue of cultures. This goal is achieved by developing the ability for intercultural communication. It is teaching organized on the basis of tasks of a communicative nature, teaching foreign language communication, using all the tasks and techniques necessary for this, that is a distinctive feature of a foreign language lesson.

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The humanistic approach involves learner-centered learning. This means that learning, or more precisely, students interacting with each other, is the center of cognitive activity in the lesson. The initial stage of teaching a second foreign language in secondary school is understood as the period of studying a second foreign language, which makes it possible to lay the foundations of communicative competence, necessary and sufficient for their further development and improvement in the course of studying that subject.

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